

Focus Group and Interview Guide for Chronic Disease mHealth Study

Semi-structured protocol for exploring experiences, needs, and challenges related to chronic disease self-management and mobile health applications.

Document Overview

- Purpose: To support focus groups and interviews exploring experiences, needs, challenges, and preferences related to chronic disease self-management and mHealth.
- Use: The same core questions can be used for both focus groups and one-to-one interviews.

1. Study Aim

This guide supports data collection on how people living with chronic conditions experience and use mobile health applications, how these tools fit into everyday health management, and what kinds of needs, barriers, and support arrangements should be considered in future design and development. The questions are intentionally broad and open-ended so that participants can describe their lived experiences in their own terms.

2. Session Outline

1. Welcome and introduction of the researchers.
2. Brief explanation of the study purpose and what will happen during the session.
3. Opportunity for participants to ask questions about the explanatory statement and consent form.
4. Confirm consent to participate and to audio recording, then start recording if permitted.
5. Conduct the semi-structured discussion.
6. Summarise key points and invite any final comments.
7. Explain next steps, stop recording, and thank participants.

3. Semi-Structured Question Guide

Part A. Participant Context and Health Management

- Could you briefly tell us about your health condition or conditions and how they affect your day-to-day life?
 - Probe: Has your condition changed over time?

- Probe: Are there particular symptoms, situations, or periods that make self-management easier or harder?
- What kinds of tasks do you regularly do to manage your health?
 - Probe: For example, monitoring symptoms, medication, appointments, exercise, diet, or communication with clinicians.
 - Probe: Which of these tasks feel easy, and which feel demanding or stressful?
- How would you describe your general approach to managing your health?
 - Probe: Do you tend to plan ahead and monitor things proactively, or do you usually respond when a problem arises?
 - Probe: What affects your motivation to keep track of your health over time?

Part B. Experience with mHealth Applications

- What kinds of mHealth apps or digital tools have you used, if any?
 - Probe: What did you use them for?
 - Probe: How often did you use them and for how long?
- Thinking about your experience, what features or aspects of these apps have been most useful to you?
 - Probe: What made them useful in your situation or routine?
- What aspects of these apps have been frustrating, difficult, or unsuitable for you?
 - Probe: Were there features that felt too complex, too demanding, unclear, or not relevant to your needs?
 - Probe: Were there times when your condition, symptoms, or treatment routine affected how you could use the app?

Part C. Everyday Experience of Using mHealth

- Do you find that your health condition affects the way you use mobile health apps, or what you need from them?
 - Probe: changes in symptoms, energy, concentration, routines, or managing more than one condition.
- Are there times when other people are involved in your health management or in using an app with you?
 - Probe: family members, carers, friends, or clinicians.
 - Probe: What kind of support do they provide, if any?
- How do you usually feel when using mobile health apps or digital health features?
 - Probe: What makes the experience comfortable, uncomfortable, easy, or difficult?
 - Probe: Does this change depending on the type of task or feature?
- What makes you feel comfortable or uncomfortable relying on information or features in an mHealth app?

- Probe: privacy, data sharing, accuracy, reliability, or whether you understand what the app is doing.
- Probe: What would make you feel more confident using it?
- When using an mHealth app, do you prefer to manage things yourself step by step, or would you rather the app do more automatically?
 - Probe: Are there some parts where you want more control and others where you want less effort?
 - Probe: How much customisation or guidance feels right for you?
- Are there personal, family, language, or community factors that affect how you would like an mHealth app to work?
 - Probe: language preference, family involvement, preferred tone, or the kinds of advice and support that feel appropriate to you.

Part D. Requirements and Design Implications

> SUPPORT MATERIAL <

We are now going to show you video with three types of adaptation can happen on the user interface. We know that some of the features illustrated have been previously discussed in the survey, but we would like you to consider them again.

There are three type adaptation we want to show to the participants, we will ask the following questions after presenting the adaptation video.

- What do you think about these adaptations?
 - a. In your opinion, are they useful? do you notice some of them in your experience of using applications?
 - b. Can you tell us in what situations would you think these adaptations are quite useful?
- In your opinion, what are the main factors that make you like or dislike these types of adaptations?
- What problems or concerns do you associate to the use of these types of adaptations?
- What are other adaptations that you would really like to see in a given mhealth application?

- Is there anything else that you would like to share or discuss about this subject?